

This document contains additional material to the submission of the paper: LINDA GAUDER, CHRISTIAN KÜCHERER, DENISE JUNGER, OLIVER BURGERT: Elicitation and Documentation of Explainability Requirements in a Medical, submitted to ICSE 2025.

First iteration of the template and the guidelines

The following are excerpts extracted from the bachelor thesis and translated into English.

Figure 29: Process model for Explainability Requirement Elicitation Aid

Figure 29 depicts a method of information gathering and implementation, divided into three sections by a black fork. The upper left half defines the information gathering process, indicated by gray arrows pointing in the execution direction. It is subdivided into properties that should be fulfilled for an explanation and definition aids, which provide a selection option to pay more attention to the definition. The selection option of the definition aid is divided by an OR because a requirement should specialize, and in most cases, only one option should be chosen. An exception is the data type, as multiple data types can indeed be used for an explanation.

The individual properties are divided into separate color areas with their definition aids and associated supporting questions. The specification of the explanation is in the same color field as the purpose of the explanation, as it further specifies the purpose. The same principle is applied to the data type, which specifies the type of explanation. The order of the properties has been adapted to the scenarios, as in SLR11 [10] and SLR20 [4], which use a specific order for information gathering.

It is also emphasized, reinforced by some works, that the target audience is crucial for the further course of the explanation, as in SLR3 [29], SLR6 [27], SLR9 [37], and SLR17 [11]. This important factor emphasizes the beginning of information research on the target audience. Based on SLR5 [14], the properties and definition aids were built. The definition aids were expanded for the target audience of the explanation and purpose of the explanation from SLR20 [4]. SLR20 [4] also suggested a new property through the explaining unit and the target environment since this is used as information in the template from SLR20. The definition aid for the explaining unit was set by Balasubramaniam et al. [4], while the definition aid for the target environment uses Balzert [5] as an information provider. SLR6 [27] expands the type of explanation and the specification of the explanation, while SLR3 [29], SLR9 [37], SLR17 [11], and SLR18 [35] only expand the type of explanation. SLR2 [3] also expands the type of explanation to include the auditory aspect and the data type to include audio. The individual properties refer to their respective definition aids with black arrows, which then point to their specification with a black arrow. The contents of the extensions can be found in the results of the data analysis from the previous chapter.

The upper right half represents two implementation methods, each representing two different approaches. These scenarios can serve for requirement identification. The first method is marked in blue and defined by SLR11 [10]. Black arrows again indicate the execution direction. The first three areas are filled in and can gather information from the properties. The associated areas are marked, and the area is in a color-matched blue above. The following two areas of the blue scenario are bordered in blue to symbolize their belonging. They use the previously obtained information and now implement it. Separated by OR after the blue scenario is a template from SLR20 [4]. This is marked in orange, and the information to be used

is again found in the properties. The areas are marked with the information to be used in orange font.

The lower part of the fork is defined by questions. They were adopted for the areas target audience of the explanation, purpose of the explanation/specification of the explanation, type of explanation, and the scenario from SLR21 [25]. New questions were created for the properties explaining unit and target environment since there were no questions for these areas. The area is defined by questions for information definition. The included questions are intended to aid understanding of the individual properties and lead to better implementation. Using the questions, it can also be checked whether the necessary information from the properties has been collected. They should lead to an understanding of the definition aids rather than simply selecting the desired ones. Under the questions for each property and the scenario, the overarching question is placed. This applies to all areas and must be additionally checked since too much information can also be misleading [10]. Therefore, unnecessary information should not be passed on.

The individual definitions of the terms from Figure 29 are presented in a definition in Table 22. The overarching terms are highlighted in gray to indicate that the subsequent terms belong to this area. The coloring of the other terms is based on that of Figure 29 to maintain recognition of the assignment.

Terminology	Definition
Explanation of the desiderata	Desiderata are the wishes of the interest groups. Making these wishes explainable is the overarching goal.
Goals of the declaration	The overarching goal is divided into several individual goals, which are reflected in the properties.
Realisation of the goals	The implementation provides schemas that use the information collected from the properties to define requirements.
Properties	Represents areas of a declaration that should be defined for a compact declaration.
Target group of the declaration	The target group defines people and helps to determine the knowledge required for the explanation and the person's existing prior knowledge.
Type of addressee	This is the information provision area of the person to be addressed of a declaration for the template within the scenario.
Target groups Setting	Is the information provision area that enriches the first element of the blue scenario with information.
Purpose of the declaration	Should integrate when and how the system is to be explained.
Specification of the declaration	Specifies the purpose of the declaration to include structural aspects.
Aspect	Is the scope of information used to determine the purpose of a declaration for the template within the scenario.
Goals of the target group	Is the information provision area that enriches the second element of the blue scenario with information.
Type of declaration	Defines the way in which a declaration can be made.
Datatype	Specifies the type of a declaration to the data type that passes variables from different categories of representations.
Context	This is the information output area used to determine the representation of an explanation for the template within the scenario.
Skills of the target group	Is the information provision area that enriches the third element of the blue scenario with information.
Explaining unit	Defines the unit that represents an explanation of the system.

Explainer	This is the information output area of the unit to be determined, which provides an explanation for the template within the scenario.
Target environment	Defines an environment of the system.
System	This is the information provision area that determines the environment of an explanation for the template within the scenario.
Scenario	The scenario defines different schemes to collect requirements based on the defined information.
Definition aids	These are selection options for each property, which are intended to simplify the definition of requirements.
Developer	Is a person who is involved in the creation of the software.
Consumers	Is a person who buys the system for use.
Users	Is a person who uses the system.
Stakeholders	Is a person who has an interest in the system.
Partner	Is a person who is involved in the creation of the system.
Employees	Is a person who works for the organisation or company that creates the system.
White-Box Systems Creation	The interpretability methods of white-box models are to be improved.
Black-Box Systems Explanation	To improve the interpretability of black box models.
Increase the fairness of the system	The interpretability of the system is related to the social and ethical impact of algorithms in terms of fairness and evaluates the system for impartiality and discrimination against users.
Checking the sensitivity of the prediction	The trustworthiness of predictions/results of the system must be checked for stability.
Assessment of the impact	The system has an impact on society. The assessment of the impact should be explained.
Gaining the trust of users	Explaining the system to the target group is crucial to gaining their trust.
Increase system security	Data protection can be strained by ensuring transparency through declarations.

Increase traceability	The system should be comprehensible in all areas and be able to explain the individual decisions that lead to the result.
Increase comprehensibility	The purpose of comprehensibility is to convey to people the where and why of using the system and to make the system as such understandable.
Purpose of the system	The purpose of the system must be clearly defined and relates above all to how and why the system is used.
Role and capability of the system	It must be defined when the system issues recommendations and when it returns a clear decision.
Inputs from the system	The inputs used in the system should be displayed.
Outputs of the system	The expenses received in the system should be displayed.
Behaviour of the system	The behaviour of the system should include information about how the system works.
Algorithms of the system	The presentation of the algorithms, especially their inner workings, must be reproduced.
System data used	The data used within the system must be visualised. This mainly relates to where and how the data is used. Also the accuracy of the data used.
Limitations of the system	It should be shown how far-reaching the system is in relation to the boundaries.
Model specific	Should set whether the declaration can be applied to an individual area.
Model agnostic	Should set whether the declaration can be applied to each area.
Structure of the declaration	The structure is made up of several attributes. The aim is to define which attributes within the target group and the context can be appropriately selected for the explanation.
Local	Defines a declaration that deals with individual cases in the system.
Global	Defines an explanation that includes the entire system.
Causal/Mechanical	It is defined by the relationship, A causes B to do C.
Functional/Technological	It is defined by the relationship, A did B because of function C.
Intentional	It is defined by the relationship, A did B because C wanted or needed it.
Textual	Is a type of explanation in text form.
Visual	Is a type of explanation in visual form.

Auditive	Is a kind of explanation in audible form.
Numerical	Is a type of explanation based on numbers.
Rule based	Is a type of explanation based on rules.
Mixed	Is a type of declaration which can consist of several types of declaration.
Counterfactual explanation	Is a representation of the explanation that refers to what is not given.
Conflict relationship	Is a representation of the explanation that supports the explanation of how conditions can be influenced.
Correlation coefficients	Is a representation of the explanation that conveys the relationship between two variables through the correlation coefficient.
Other	The presentation of the declaration may deviate from the above options and it is possible to formulate the declaration under a different aspect.
Table	Is a form of representation by the type of table that must be processed by the system.
Text	Is a form of representation by the type of text that must be processed by the system.
Image	Is a form of representation by the type of image that must be processed by the system.
Graphic	Is a form of representation by the type of graphic that must be processed by the system.
Audio	Is a form of representation by the type of audio that must be processed by the system.
AI that explains itself	Is a system possibility to create the declaration by an AI.
Explainability tool	Is a system option to create the declaration using a tool.
People	Is a system possibility to create the declaration by a human being.
Applicationsoftware	Is software that is intended to solve the user's tasks with the help of computer systems. Application software can be divided into six dimensions of software complexity, which are reused in the individual subcategories.
Systemsoftware	Is software that enables the operation and maintenance, as well as the addition of functional capabilities for special hardware or hardware families.

Administrative, commercial, business-orientated software	Is software that is characterised by the complexity of the data, which represents a multitude of data structures or very complex data structures, and the complexity of the functions, which contains a multitude of functions in the software.
Technical-scientific software	Is software that is characterised by the complexity of the functions, which contains a large number of functions in the software and the complexity of the algorithms, which, for example, process complex numerical calculations in the system.
Software-intensive systems	Is software that is characterised by the complexity of the algorithms that, for example, process complex numerical calculations in the system, the complexity of the system environment, which is characterised by other systems that are embedded in one and have thus become subcomponents of it. And the complexity of the time-dependent behaviour, which is represented by adjustments to the data in a chronological sequence, such as concurrent processes, synchronisation, mutual exclusion and similar.
GUI-intensive software	Is software that is characterised by the complexity of the user interface and interaction, which reflects a complex interaction between user and system.
Computer platform	Refers to software that deals with control programmes, such as the operating system on a computer platform. These also concern the maintenance of these.
Special hardware	Refers to software that deals with utilities, such as utilities, management and editors on specific hardware such as a GPU. These also concern the maintenance of these.
Hardware family	Refers to software that establishes a connection between the hardware of a certain hardware family in order to manage, control and connect it.
Target group Identify settings	Presentation to gain an understanding of the environment and context of the interest group.
Identifying the goals of the target group	Presentation to identify the goals and sub-goals of the interest group and the cognitive tasks that are carried out in their environment. These should be sorted in chronological order.
Identifying the skills of the target group	Presentation to identify features of existing instruments used by stakeholders.

Create scenario	Presentation to identify the scenarios that represent the processes and cognitive tasks of the stakeholder group, which are derived from the stakeholder group's attitudes, goals and tools.
Use scenario to identify requirements	Creation of requirements through identification by means of interviews, prototypes, surveys and anthropomorphism studies (attribution of the human being to non-human entities).
As <type of addressee> I would like to receive explanations about an <aspect> of a <system> from an <explainer> in a <context>	Is a template for the requirements elicitation, which is filled in by inserting the information.
Questions about the definition of information	The area is intended to create an understanding of the individual properties and is set by questions which are intended to be used to process the evaluation, adaptation, selection and development of the information of the areas.
Overarching question	Is an area that is set by a question that serves for all properties. This is intended to help define the importance of the information in order to avoid unnecessary explanations and minimise the risk of overloading.
OR	Logical Or for a selection of elements.
AND	Logical And for a selection of elements.

Table 22 Definition of the process model for the explainability requirement survey help in Fig. 2